

Offshore Installation of Piles in Egypt

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ABSTRACT

The paper contains the case history of the installation and testing of offshore foundation piles in the Gulf of Suez in Egypt. For the installation of two offshore jackets for the oil and gas industry piles of over 100 m length had to be driven. Because of this length the piles were driven in sections, with pile driving monitoring throughout the entire installation.

The soil investigation at the project site indicated the potential for voids at several depth as the cone resistance became as low as close to zero in a silt layer from 73,5 till 100 m below seabed.

The papers show the results of the pile driving monitoring. At final penetration depth restrikes were performed to determine the pile capacity of the pile through a Dynamic Load Test (or High Strain Dynamic Test). The process of modelling the soil strata, the adjustments to that soil model as part of the signal matching process as well as a discussion of the generated test results are also presented in the paper.

Keywords: DLT, PDA, Dynamic Load Testing, offshore, Signal Matching

1. INTRODUCTION

For the foundation of two offshore platforms in the Gulf of Suez, Offshore Egypt, open ended steel piles have been installed. These piles have a diameter of 0.762 m (30"), and pile lengths around 127 m. The wall thicknesses are 38,1 mm (1,5") (standard dimension ratio SDR, nominal diameter to wall thickness ratio of 20). During installation measurements have been performed to control the installation process. And after installation, redrives have been performed in order to check the axial bearing capacity of these piles.

In this paper results, considerations and conclusions are given based on this specific case.

2. GEOTECHNICAL SURVEY

At the Gulf of Suez, the Arabian Tectonic Plate meets the African Tectonic Plate. During the formation of the Gulf of Suez, the intra-continental rift led to high variable soil composition and geotechnical properties of the seabed. Even the existence of voids at lower (foundation) levels can be expected. The soil investigation at the project site indicated the potential for those voids and gas filled voids at several depths, as the cone resistance became as low as close to zero in a silt layer from 73,5 till 100 m below seabed.

For the geotechnical survey soil investigation with both in-situ testing and laboratory tests have been performed. The in-situ soil investigation consisted of on-site sampling and in situ testing

included alternating downhole sampling and cone penetration testing (CPT).

Figure 1. One of the boreholes of the soil investigation

Based on these test results, the pile dimensions have been designed. Piles have a diameter of 0.762 m (30"), and pile lengths around 127 m. The wall thicknesses are 38,1 mm (1,5"). A driveability study has been performed by the contractor in order to optimize pile installation, avoid unexpected events during installation and avoidance of preliminary refusal.

3. TEST CAMPAIGN

For the purpose of quality control, a pile testing campaign has been setup based on measurements during and after installation (including redrives). The measurements during driving were performed to control the pile stresses, check the performance of the hammer, etc. The measurements during the redrives are performed to derive an estimate of the static capacity of the foundation piles. The results of these tests (so called Dynamic Load Tests or High Strain Dynamic Tests) proof the design. By testing the installed pile, it is checked if the total of assumptions in soil characterization, design parameters, design method and engineering judgement has led to a safe and sound foundation.

4. MONITORING THE PILE DRIVING PROCESS

The 4 foundation piles of each jacket are driven in sections. The first two sections, until 50 m seabed penetration were driven with a Delmag D80-12. After welding the third and fourth section on the pile, the pile was driven to final penetration with one of the two on board available Menck steam hammers: a Menck MRBS3000 or a Menck MRBS3900.

Figure 2. monitoring during driving, applying a steam hammer to the piles

During installation the pile has been instrumented with 2 strain and 2 accelerometers of the Allnamics PDA monitoring system. During driving the parameters were derived from the measured signals, including:

- Impact velocity in the pile
- Transferred energy in the pile
- System efficiency regards to the nominal power of the hammer, i.e ratio of effective

transferred energy and the nominal energy of the hammer

- Force time curve
- Pile stresses measured at pile top and estimated at other locations in the pile
- Estimate of soil resistance during driving

Fig. 2. Typical signals for forces and velocities, based on the measured strain and acceleration signals. First and last blow with the Menck MRBS 3000 steam hammer of one of the piles. No shaft friction over the meters up to mud/ground level.

5. CONTROL OF THE PILE STRESSES

The strains at sensor level near the top of the pile are directly measured. Assuming a Young's modulus of 210.000 MPa show the stresses at the monitoring level.

By applying stress wave analysis, an estimate can be made for maximum stresses at other levels in the pile. The compression stresses at the top of the pile are mainly caused by the impact of the hammer. Tension stresses in the pile and compression stresses at the toe are mainly influenced by the toe resistance of the soil.

In all measured piles of this project, the driving stresses had to be below 90% of the yield stress of 390 MPa. As can be seen in Fig. 1, the driving stresses during the driving process led to driving maximum stresses of approximate

200 MPa, with an average of 150 MPa for most of the penetration range.

6. CONTROL OF HAMMER PERFORMANCE

Monitoring the pile during installation will also give an indication of the hammer performance. The effectiveness of a pile driving hammer is not just the ram mass nor impact speed, but basically the amount of energy that enters the pile to overcome soil resistance. That energy, entru energy, is monitored during PDA. In this project it worked out that the steam hammer was functioning irregularly. Lower energy in the pile led to higher blow counts and the risk of an early refusal.

Fig. 1. Monitored maximum pile stresses at sensor level, based on measured strains.

The specifications of the hammers used in this project are given **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** It has to be taken into account that rated energies cannot be compared directly. The 272 kNm rated energy of the D-80 diesel hammer seems at first sight 60% of that of the MRBS 3000. However, a diesel hammer is a one stroke combustion motor, burning diesel to lift the ram. During downward movement of the ram, the valves of the combustion chamber will be closed. In the closed combustion chamber the pressure will increase rapidly, slowing down the impact ram. As a result, the impact energy is much lower than the rated energy. It is well known that often

Figure 3. Sensors for strain and accelerations are mounted in the pile. The PDR data recorder stores the signals internally and send them real-time wireless to the monitoring computer

approximately 50% (or less) of the rated energy can be effective in the pile (as entru energy).

Steam hammers have a different working principle. The steam is the driving force of the uplift of the ram. Once the ram is in the highest position, gravity will accelerate the ram until impact. The rated energy of the ram can be fully mobilized as impact energy (except energy losses due to friction, etc.).

Table 1. Hammer Specs

		Drop Height [m]	Ram mass [kg]	Rated Energy [kNm]	Blow rate [bl/min]
Delmag	D-80-12	3.4	8,000	272	36 - 45
Menck	MRBS 3000	1.5	30,000	450	42
Menck	MRBS 3900	1.8	39,400	709	34

The monitored transferred energy of the diesel hammer had an average of approximate 40 kNm for the first pile section. An entru ratio (ratio entru energy/rated energy) of 15% during the first pile. Due to the limited soil resistance, the diesel hammer didn't come to maximum performance (blow rates of 55-58 blows/minute). From the second add-on and subsequent add-ons, the performance of the diesel hammer increased. Due to higher soil resistance, the blow rated dropped tot app 40 blows/minute, with increased entru energy up tot (average) 85 kNm (an entru ratio of app 30%).

The two steam hammers showed low performance. The hammers were driving irregular and the monitored entru energy in the piles were much less than expected. Steam leakage in the

system, especially leakage of the steam hoses caused insufficient supply of steam for a smooth operation.

In the end piles were driven until final penetration. The results of the measurements show clearly the irregular hammer performance over the penetration depth (Fig. 4).

7. DYNAMIC LOAD TESTING (HSDT)

The main purposes of performing pile monitoring during and after installation are quality control of the installation process during driving, and obtaining the pile capacity (static behaviour) after installation. The first part is often indicated as PDA, or Pile Driving Analysis. The second part is often called DLT or HSDT, Dynamic Load Testing or High Strain Dynamic Testing or PDA as well.

Dynamic Load Testing can be done during the last impact blows of the pile installation (end of driving) or by performing some additional blows

Fig. 3 Results for entru energy in the pile show strong variations in the drop heights of the steam hammer. Up to 67.2 m penetration depth, the MRSB 3000 has been applied, followed by the MRSB 3900

after a certain period, a redrive. The period between end of driving and redrive is often referred to the set-up period. In this period the soil recovers its strength. The time needed for full soil recovery depends on the local soil conditions, but the minimum is often taken as 2 to 3 days.

The monitored signals for strain and accelerations, are transferred to time signals for forces (by multiplying by assumed values for Youngs modulus and cross-sectional area at sensor level) and velocity (by integrating the acceleration signal). By using the stress wave theory, the measured signals can be converted in time signals for downward and upward travelling stress waves.

A downward traveling stress wave is caused by the impact of the pile driving hammer. Reflections are caused by shaft friction of the soil and impedance changes of the pile (change in cross-sectional area and material quality). As there are no reliable direct methods to derive the (static) capacity from a dynamic load test, the Signal Match technique has to be applied (see fig 5.). For this project AllWave-DLT has been used for Signal Matching on signals at end of driving and redrives,

Fig. 4. DLT Signal Match procedure

8. SOIL MODEL

The initial soil model has to be based on the results of the soil investigation. Soil layers in the model should coincide with the soil layers as indicated in the soil investigations reports. Basic formulas are used to transform soil investigation results into dynamic soil parameters. This process has been combined with engineering judgement to get a realistic initial soil model.

The initial soil model based on the soil investigations gave already an ‘acceptable’ match, although the Signal Matching has still to start. During a number of loops of changing the soil model, observing its effect, and re-adjust the soil model the iteration process ended up giving a higher quality Signal Match. See figure 6 for the match results: calculated upward traveling waves compared with measured upward travelling waves.

Some of the piles came to an early refusal. In this case the DLT helped the project. The capacity

Fig. 6 Result of the Signal Match for EOD of one of the piles: Simulated and measured upward travelling wave.

of the pile at the refusal depth was sufficient to be accepted.

9. SET UP EFFECTS

There will be a difference in test results when one of the hammer blows from the end of driving (EOD) for a certain pile section is compared to one of the first blows for the pile with the next add-on.

Between EOD and redrive on one of the piles, a set-up period of 4 days has passed. See figure 7 to the changes in yield values for the skin friction from the initial soil model (figure 7 left) to the end of the signal Matching process (figure 7 right). The latter corresponds well with the soil investigation results (figure 1)

Fig. 5 differences in mobilized resistance at restrike (left) and end of driving (right) at the same penetration depth.

10. DISCUSSION / CONCLUSION

Performing measurements during installation can have a number of goals. In this project monitoring has been part of the quality control, to control maximum piles stresses during installation. The monitoring indicated also clear the reason for the early refusal of some piles. Hammer performance could be increased based on the monitoring results for enthr energy. The capacity based on Signal Matches on signals of redrives showed that the piles had sufficient bearing capacity, even at the higher penetration levels due to early refusals.

One of these: Steam hammer in use for offshore pile installation

Each jacket is pinned to the subsoil by piles of more than 100 m length

Wireless data connection with the monitoring computer on the barge, and redundancy by data storage in the data acquisition unit, makes the life's of testing engineers easier

Signal Matching NAO platform P1A-3 restrike 26-10-2017

P1A-3
plugged, blow 2190 (EOD?)

EOD versus Restrike of pile 3
plugged, blow 2190 (EOD?)

P1A-3

Signal Matching NAO platform aug 2017 P1A-3 plugging

Pile P1A-3

File P1B-4

EOD:

BLOW RESULTS

File Number	P1B-4 (plugged)
Blow Number	1593
Max. Transf. Energy 2,0L/c	423,1 [kNm]
Penetration Pile Toe	68,500 [m]
Maximum Pile Top Displ.	51,4 [mm]
Maximum Pile Toe Displ.	3,9 [mm]

SOIL RESISTANCE RESULTS

Mobilized Static Resistance	24,479 [MN]
Mob. Static Resistance Toe	22,455 [MN]
Mob. Static Resist. Shaft	2,023 [MN]
Mob. Static Resistance Toe	49,2 [MPa]

Restrike (after 4 days):

BLOW RESULTS

File Number	P1B-4 (restrike 4 days)
Blow Number	1593
Max. Transf. Energy 2,0L/c	408,3 [kNm]
Penetration Pile Toe	68,500 [m]
Maximum Pile Top Displ.	51,2 [mm]
Maximum Pile Toe Displ.	3,2 [mm]

SOIL RESISTANCE RESULTS

Mobilized Static Resistance	24,537 [MN]
Mob. Static Resistance Toe	22,432 [MN]
Mob. Static Resist. Shaft	2,105 [MN]
Mob. Static Resistance Toe	258,9 [MPa]

Vraag: 2x dezelfde blow, dus twee keer hetzelfde resultaat?

P-2A-4

EOD (blow 2190)

BLOW RESULTS

File Number	P2A-4 (plugged)
Blow Number	2190
Max. Transf. Energy 2,0L/c	454,1 [kJm]
Penetration Pile Toe	70,400 [m]
Maximum Pile Top Displ.	51,6 [mm]
Maximum Pile Toe Displ.	1,6 [mm]

SOIL RESISTANCE RESULTS

Mobilized Static Resistance	25,140 [MN]
Mob. Static Resistance Toe	20,750 [MN]
Mob. Static Resist. Shaft	4,390 [MN]
Mob. Static Resistance Toe	45,5 [MPa]

Restrike (blow 786)

BLOW RESULTS

File Number	P2A-4 (restrike)
Blow Number	786
Max. Transf. Energy 2,0L/c	442,3 [kJm]
Penetration Pile Toe	70,400 [m]
Maximum Pile Top Displ.	50,2 [mm]
Maximum Pile Toe Displ.	1,6 [mm]

SOIL RESISTANCE RESULTS

Mobilized Static Resistance	22,559 [MN]
Mob. Static Resistance Toe	17,462 [MN]
Mob. Static Resist. Shaft	5,097 [MN]
Mob. Static Resistance Toe	201,5 [MPa]

Soi model input AllWave-DL, DLT P-2A-4
Aug 2017 restrrike 1st attempt manual

Depth from to [m]	Ground unit name	Ground unit behaviour	γ [kN/m ³]	c_u [kPa]	β [-]	f_{lim} [kPa]	N_q [-]	q_{lim} [MPa]
0.0 - 3.0	Shell/Coral debris	Frictional	16.0 - 16.0	-	0.16	23	8	0.9
3.0 - 7.0	Calcarenite	Frictional	19.5 - 19.5	-	0.20	30	8	0.9
7.0 - 13.5	Sand/Silt	Frictional	17.0 - 17.0	-	0.16	23	8	0.9
13.5 - 16.0	Calcarenite	Frictional	19.5 - 19.5	-	0.19	27	8	1.8
16.0 - 21.5	Coral debris	Frictional	16.0 - 16.0	-	0.15	23	8	1.8
21.5 - 30.5	Sand	Frictional	21.0 - 21.0	-	0.25	42	8	1.8
30.5 - 40.7	Silt/Clay	Cohesive	19.5 - 19.5	200 - 200	-	100 - 100	-	1.8
40.7 - 45.4	Sand	Frictional	19.0 - 19.0	-	0.23	36	8	1.8
45.4 - 47.5	Clay	Cohesive	17.5 - 17.5	200 - 200	-	100 - 100	-	1.8
47.5 - 51.0	Silt	Frictional	20.0 - 20.0	-	0.20	43	20	1.8

Depth from to [m]	Ground unit name	Ground unit behaviour	γ [kN/m ³]	c_u [kPa]	β [-]	f_{lim} [kPa]
51.0 - 58.5	Sand	Frictional	19.5 - 19.5	-	0.56	115
58.5 - 61.3	Silt	Cohesive	19.0 - 19.0	200 - 200	-	100 - 100
61.3 - 63.0	Silt	Frictional	19.0 - 19.0	-	0.18	33
63.0 - 69.7	Clay/Silt	Cohesive	19.0 - 19.0	230 - 230	-	115 - 115
69.7 - 75.0	Sand	Frictional	20.5 - 20.5	-	0.15	19
75.0 - 82.0	Sand	Frictional	20.5 - 20.5	-	0.46	96
82.0 - 96.2	Clay	Cohesive	19.0 - 19.0	300 - 300	-	150 - 150
96.2 - 99.2	Gypsum/Clay	Frictional	18.0 - 18.0	-	0.30	115

Uit N6080_01 (4) HH

